

DIGITIZED READING MATERIAL: AN INTERACTIVE TOOL ON PHONEMIC AWARENESS AND READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Filipino students are unable to identify and manipulate phonemes, thereby impairing their reading comprehension skills. In response, the research "Digitized Reading Material: An Interactive Tool for Phonemic Awareness and Reading Comprehension Skills" examines the effectiveness of a digitized reading intervention on these skills. The research employed a one-group pre-test and post-test design to compare (43) Grade 7 students of Tuyongan Integrated School (2024-2025). One group pretest-posttest design observes one group without using a control group. The respondents are selected based on the PHIL-IRI Group Screening Test, a Department of Education assessment tool. The instrument is a researcher's made questionnaire and was validated by a panel of experts, and underwent pilot testing for reliability test. The following are the essential findings of the investigation: During the Pre-test, the respondents had an "average" performance indicating the respondents could manipulate sounds in words at a minimum level but still experienced difficulties with more challenging phonemic activities. Further, Post- test Performance, the respondents performed at a "high" level after the intervention. The capacity of the respondents to manage sounds in words increased immensely. They can now decode words reliably, which increases their reading comprehension and also, exhibit higher abilities in determining key concepts and analyzing information. Furthermore, there was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test performances of the respondents. The study's results underscore the positive effect of

digitized reading material in the phonemic awareness and reading comprehension skills of the respondents.

Keywords: *Digitized Material, Reading Comprehension, Phonemic Awareness*

INTRODUCTION

Current accounts shows that literacy remains a significant challenge in the Philippines' educational system. Recent data indicates that many students, particularly in public schools, perform below the expected reading proficiency levels for their grade (Chi, 2024). Literacy gap has become more pronounced, especially among learners in rural areas like Toyungan, Calinog, Iloilo, where access to diverse learning resources may be limited. This scenario is not far from what the learners of Tuyongan Integrated School have been experiencing especially the Grade7 learners. Integrated schools provide education from preschool/kindergarten through high school, meaning students can complete their entire basic education journey at the same location. Based on the result of their Group Screening Test (GST) more than half of the class got a score of below 14 which is ground for further assessment the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Group Screening Test (GST) is a 20-item, group-administered reading comprehension assessment used to identify students who may need further, individual testing while Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is a classroom-based assessment tool used by the Department of Education (DepEd) to measure and describe students' reading performance, helping teachers design appropriate reading instruction (Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual 2018).

According to McNamara cited in Cubillas et al. (2019), comprehension is not always effortless and fast. When beginning readers struggle over individual words, reading is slowed to a near halt and deeper levels of comprehension are seriously compromised (Cubillas 2019). Despite various reading intervention programs in place, many students continue to struggle with reading comprehension even when they can decode words. Decoding involves breaking a word into its individual sounds and then blending those sounds together to form the word. It is known that problems in phonological awareness affect decoding, as well as deficits in grammar, semantics and narrative discourse impact reading comprehension (De Barbieri Ortiz 2016). On the other hand, Elhassan et al. (2017) highlighted that, having moderate reading fluency, phonological awareness significantly contributed to phonological decoding but not to other reading measures.

This persistent challenge indicates a need for new literacy teaching strategies to help students with both word identification and comprehension. The separation between decoding skills and text comprehension ability, known as 'word-level reading' difficulty, requires specific instructional approaches that foster both phonemic awareness and direct application to text reading (Chi, 2024). Thus, Doty (2024) highlighted those interventions into phonemic awareness greatly enhanced decoding skills and reading acquisition among challenged readers or readers having difficulties. This suggests that integration of modified intervention must be inconsideration to foster better learning process, digitized reading material can be one of which.

The emergence of digital technologies presents potential solutions to these literacy issues. Electronic books can provide multimedia and interactive content tailored to focus on specific areas of literacy like phonemic awareness and reading comprehension. Research by Jamshidifarsani et al. (2019) through a meta-synthesis of 42 studies confirmed that when properly integrated into teaching and learning, technology offers effective and enjoyable ways of learning literacy. These technologies can provide immediate feedback, responsive learning experiences, and multiple means of text representation that could particularly benefit struggling readers. This research is directly connected to the problem of phonemic awareness and reading skill as it investigates how computer technologies, especially electronic books, can be used as efficient means of literacy acquisition.

Furthermore, Lysenko and Abrami's (2014) meta-analysis of two instructional web-based applications demonstrated positive results in elementary students' reading skills. Their study of 261 students from grades 2 through 6 showed that students using these technologies gained more vocabulary and reading comprehension skills than non-users. In the same way, this current study explores how digitized reading materials enhance phonemic awareness and understanding in students. Both studies highlight the role of technology in literacy acquisition through offering interactive and motivating tools that aid children in deciphering words, identifying sounds, and improving comprehension of texts. Lysenko and Abrami's findings corroborate the positive effect of digital interventions on reading instruction, which is consistent with the purpose of the current study to enhance literacy skills using digitized material. Moreover, Donnelly et al. (2020) highlighted that integrating digital tools demonstrated significant improvement in pseudoword decoding among the intervention group, providing concrete evidence technological interventions can create more effective learning environments than traditional methods alone.

However, there remains a gap in understanding how digitized reading materials can effectively address both phonemic awareness and reading comprehension simultaneously, particularly in the Philippine context. While separate studies show the benefits of technology in either phonemic awareness or reading comprehension, limited research exists on integrated digital approaches that target both skills together, especially for struggling readers in rural Philippine schools.

Therefore, this research is especially relevant in that it aims to close the research gap by creating and testing digitized reading materials that combine both reading comprehension and phonemic awareness instruction. This research was especially strong in that it attempted to solve crucial questions surrounding the use of digital tools in optimal holistic literacy development. Although technology has already demonstrated the potential to develop reading skills, it is unknown how to structure digital materials in a way that both enhances phonemic awareness and reading comprehension at the same time. Examining this problem within the Philippine setting, where literacy development was an issue for numerous students, increases the significance of this study.

Research Questions

This single group pre-test and post-test study aimed to determine the effect of the Digitized Reading Tool among the respondents of Toyungan Integrated School in the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Pre-Test Performance of the respondents?
2. What is the Post-Test Performance of the respondents?
3. Is there a significant difference in the Pre and Post Performance of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

This One Group Pre-Test Post-Test study aimed to determine the effect of digitized reading material on phonemic awareness and reading comprehension skills among the respondents. One Group Pre-Test and Post Test design where the dependent variable is measured once before the treatment is implemented and once after it is implemented (Canaria et al. 2022). One group pretest-posttest design observes one group without using a control group (Patmanthara et al. (2019).

Participants

The research participants were the forty-three (43) officially enrolled Grade 7 learners of Tuyongan Integrated School, Schools District of Calinog I, Schools Division of Iloilo for the School Year 2024-2025.

Moreover, other sources of the data were the result of their Pre-test and Post-Test. Thus, two (2) purposively selected Grammar Expert evaluated the Pre-Test and Post-Test Questionnaire and the researcher's made questionnaire undergone the Pilot Testing. Also, four (4) technologically inclined reading teachers evaluated the developed digitized reading materials using the adopted evaluation tool of the West Visayas State University for non-printed instructional materials.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, permission to conduct the research study were secured by the researcher. Upon the approval and the validation of the questionnaire was done the Researcher's made Questionnaires were distributed for Pilot Testing at Malitbog National High School. After the result of the pilot test has been determined the researcher secured the parental consent and conducted the pre-test. Moreover, After the pre-test had been administered and result were tabulated, the researcher conducted the validated 20 days intervention. After which, the researcher conducted the post-test. After the test had been administered, the questionnaires were gathered and result were tabulated and

presented in accordance with the method adopted for analysis and interpretation. The data were then subjected to appropriate statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Science Software (SPSS)

Data Analysis Procedure

The quantitative data gathered from the Pre-Test Post-Test results of the learners were subjected to quantitative data analysis. The Means were employed to determine the level of respondents' Pre-Test and post-test Performances. Also, Standard Deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the scores of the respondents in terms of their performances.

Moreover, Dependent t-Test was used to determine the significance of the differences in the pre-test and post-test performances of the respondents because the data were taken from the same group and they are found to be normally distributed.

RESULTS

Descriptive Data Analysis

The Pre-Test Performance of The Respondents

Table 1 shows the Pre-Test Performance of the Respondents. The result showed that the respondents have an "Average" performance (M=20.56, Sd=5.84). This means the respondents were able to identify and manipulate sounds in words at a minimum level but still experienced difficulties with more challenging phonemic activities and also, they can comprehend the gist of a text but were challenged by more advanced skills.

According to Elhassan et al. (2017) found that, having moderate reading fluency, phonological awareness significantly contributed to phonological decoding but not to other reading measures. This suggests that, although these children are able to perform basic phonemic activities, they might have difficulty with more complex reading exercises.

Table 1
The Pre-Test Performance of The Respondents

Category	Mean	Description	SD
Pre-Test	20.56	Average	5.84

Suggested Scale:

Mean	Description
40.01 – 50.00	Very High
30.01 – 40.00	High
20.01 – 30.00	Average
10.01 – 20.00	Low
0.00 – 10.00	Very Low

The Post-Test Performance of The Respondents

Table 2 shows the Post-Test Performance of the Respondents. The result showed that the respondents have “High” performance (M=37.53, Sd=5.13) level after the intervention was implemented. This means the capacity of the respondents to manage sounds in words increased immensely. They are now able to decode words reliably, which increased their reading comprehension and also, they exhibit higher abilities in determining key concepts and analyzing information.

According to Doty (2024) the study found that interventions into phonemic awareness greatly enhanced decoding skills and reading acquisition among challenged readers.

Table 2
The Post-Test Performance of The Respondents

Category	Mean	Description	SD
Post-Test	37.53	High	5.13

Suggested Scale:

Mean	Description
40.01 – 50.00	Very High
30.01 – 40.00	High
20.01 – 30.00	Average
10.01 – 20.00	Low
0.00 – 10.00	Very Low

Inferential Data Analysis

The Difference Between the Respondents’ Pre-Test and Post-Test Performances

Table 4 shows the difference in the performance of the respondents during pre-test and post-test. The t-Test paired Test Result revealed significant difference ($p=0.000$) between pre-test and post-test performances of the respondents. The Prevalence was less than .05 alpha. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performances of the respondents were rejected. This simply showed that the respondents’ performance in phonemic awareness and reading comprehension skills improved from pre-test to post-test.

According to Donnelly et al. (2020) found that integrating digital tools demonstrated significant improvement in pseudoword decoding among the intervention group, providing concrete evidence technological interventions can create more effective learning environments than traditional methods alone.

Table 3
Dependent t- Test for the Significance of the Differences between the Respondents' Pre-Test and Post-Test Performances

Paired Variables	Mean	Mean Difference	T	Df	Sig.
Group		16.97	28.408***	42	.000
Pre-Test	20.56				
Post-Test	37.53				

***p< .001, significant at 0.001 alpha

Conclusions

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the effect of Digitized Reading Material as an Interactive Tool in Phonemic Awareness and Reading Comprehension Skills.

The findings during Pre-test indicated that the respondents performed at "average" level. This highlights that the respondents could recognize and play with sounds in words at a fundamental level but had difficulty with more challenging phonemic tasks, and they could understand the meaning of a text but were having trouble with higher abilities. This information serves as bases to develop an intervention plan to addresses the problem. This plan may include digitized reading material focusing on phonemic awareness and reading comprehension skills as an interactive tool to foster more engaging learning environment.

The findings during the Post-test indicated that the respondents performed at "high" level. This highly indicates that the respondents' sound control in words has increased immensely. They can now consistently decode words, which has improved their reading comprehension, as well as identified key concepts and analyzed information.

The paired t-test findings indicated that there was a significant difference between respondents' pre-test and post-test performance. As a result, the significance level less than 0.05 alpha this means that the null hypothesis, which was that no significant difference would exist between the two test scores, was rejected.

Furthermore, the results further indicated that the respondents enhanced their phonemic awareness and reading comprehension skills after the intervention. Thus, digitized reading material improved substantially the phonemic awareness and understanding capabilities of the respondents. Respondents could read more effectively as they used to engage tools, translating to significant education progress.

Recommendations

This study investigated the effect of Digitized Reading Material as an Interactive Tool in Phonemic Awareness and Reading Comprehension Skills. The findings provide significant insights for a variety of educational stakeholders.

This study's findings can inform the teachers to develop a differentiated instructional material suited for average learners, whose experiencing difficulties and needed further assistance. Material that can be used in fostering phonemic awareness and reading comprehension as the basic skills needed in literacy development. Transforming reading materials into digitized reading tool can foster a deeper understanding and more engaging learning process.

The research highlights the positive effect of digitized reading material in fostering phonemic awareness and reading comprehension of the learners. Thus, curriculum developer can consider integrating digitized reading material in literacy program. This ensures that learners engage with multi-media rich resources that enhance sound recognition, word decoding, and comprehension. Moreover, Standardized Digital Module Development can be considered which should be designed in accordance with educational standard and students' competencies These must have interactive exercises, phonemic practice, and comprehension activities to reinforce the skills of the students.

Lastly, future studies along this line should further investigate the effectiveness of digitized reading materials across grade levels and evaluate long-term effects on literacy growth. Extending the study to include younger and older children will assist in evaluating whether gains in phonemic awareness and reading comprehension similar to these may be achieved. In addition, integrating sophisticated interactive aspects such as AI-based feedback, speech recognition, and adaptive learning may assist in tailoring reading assistance and enhancing student engagement. Longitudinal studies must be conducted to determine if the increased literacy skills that have been observed persist over time and lead to long-term academic progress.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research considered the ethical needs of research. First, research respondents were given complete information on the procedures involved in the research and had to sign their consent prior to inclusion. Ethical standards also necessitated the researcher to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the subject of study. Two standards were employed in safeguarding research participants' privacy. Almost all studies protect the confidentiality of the participants; they were assured that identifying details would not be shared with anyone who was not directly engaged in the study. The stricter requirement is the principle of anonymity, which essentially mandates the participant to remain anonymous throughout the study.

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